

Comparative study of drinking water samples for detection of microbial bioloads and evaluation of antimicrobial efficacy of chlorine tablets

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Abstract: Access to safe drinking water is a critical public health priority, particularly in regions facing infrastructure challenges. This study conducted a comparative analysis of 25 drinking water samples (9 groundwater, 16 distributed systems) from West Bengal, India, to assess microbial bioload and evaluate the efficacy of chlorine tablets as a disinfectant. Physical parameters (pH, TDS, conductivity) were measured, and microbial contamination was quantified via colony-forming units (CFU). Staining techniques (Gram, acid-fast, lactophenol cotton blue) identified pathogens, while chlorine susceptibility was tested at 5, 25, 50, and 100 mg/L concentrations. Results revealed significant contamination: 72% of samples harbored biofilms sheltering pathogens like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Mycobacterium* spp., and *Escherichia coli*. Chlorine exhibited dose-dependent efficacy, achieving 85–95% microbial reduction at 100 mg/L, though biofilms and acid-fast bacteria persisted due to extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) shielding. High-risk zones included tourist sites and transport hubs. The study underscores the urgency of infrastructure upgrades, implementation of a multi-barrier approach, advanced, and policy enforcement to ensure water safety and mitigate antimicrobial resistance.

Index Terms: Microbial bioload, Drinking water safety, Chlorine disinfection, Biofilm resistance, Water contamination, Antimicrobial efficacy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Access to safe and clean drinking water is essential for public health and the prevention of waterborne diseases. Potable water must meet safety standards for direct consumption and food preparation. According to WHO guidelines, drinking water should be free from harmful levels of contaminants, including heavy metals like manganese. While these standards aim to ensure both safety and health, they may vary across regions and are subject to periodic review and updates. (1).

Clean drinking water is of utmost importance to public health and an indispensable part of the prevention of disease and overall health. Clean water availability is necessary for healthy living. The World Health Organization reckons that as many as 485,000 deaths due to diarrheal diseases are estimated to occur in the world per year due to contaminated drinking water, making the issue very essential (2).

Access to safe drinking water has both public health and economic benefits. Studies indicate that a 0.3% increase in investment in domestic water access can result in a 1% rise in GDP. Additionally, safe drinking water can reduce mortality from waterborne diseases by an average of 70%, underscoring its impact on national development and well-being. (3). Investment in clean water infrastructure and investment in treatment technology are vital for economic growth and public health, especially in developing nations and rural areas (4,5).

1.1 III Effects of Unsafe Drinking Water in Human and Animals

Drinking water, which can be "safe", can also harbour serious health hazards to human and animal life by means of some contaminants and pollutants. Faecal contamination from both human and animal sources has been linked to the incidence of enteric pathogens such as *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, and *Campylobacter* in rural water sources (6). The pathogens were found in 47.69% and 32.80% of the dry and wet season samples, respectively, showing the ongoing risk of waterborne infection.

In India, the consumption of unsafe drinking water remains a serious public health concern, particularly in rural and peri-urban regions. Waterborne diseases like diarrhoea, cholera, typhoid, and hepatitis A and E are prevalent due to microbial contamination, with children under five being the most affected. Government data indicates that over 37 million Indians are impacted annually, and diarrheal illnesses account for more than 10% of child mortality.

Contaminated water affects both human and animal health, leading to reduced livestock productivity and increased risk of zoonotic diseases such as leptospirosis and cryptosporidiosis. A 2021 study in Maharashtra linked over 25% of cattle deaths in drought-affected areas to unsafe water. Additionally, high manganese levels in drinking water—exceeding WHO limits in over 50% of tube wells in Bangladesh—have been associated with neurotoxic effects in humans.(7). The estimated hazard quotient (HQ) value of Mn was higher than unity, suggesting possible non-carcinogenic health risks to children and adults.

The so-called "safe" drinking water can cause various harmful effects on human beings and animals because of the presence of pathogens, heavy metals, and other contaminants. The results highlight the necessity for better water treatment practices, including the "Minus Approach" (8), which focuses on biologically and physically eliminating contaminants but not with excessive reliance on chemical treatments. Proper monitoring and enforcement of effective practices are required to provide access to genuinely safe drinking water and reduce the connected health risks.

Excessive use of disinfectants in water treatment can even lead to microbial resistance, which is of extreme significance to human as well as animal health. Disinfectants are of extreme significance in reducing pathogenic microorganisms to safe levels and preventing the spread of infection. Bacteria, however, have shown an incredible ability to develop resistance against chemical stress caused by biocides, which could lead to reduced susceptibility to the agents (9).

Resistance has also been manifested as large-scale deviations in minimum inhibitory concentrations of chlorhexidine disinfectants and triclosan-disinfectant-based products (9). The resistance has the capacity to be cross-transferred out of the domain of disinfectants to antibiotics, leading to the development of multidrug-resistant pathogens that are highly resistant to treatment (10). This is made worse by the broad use of antibiotics in animal farms and poultry, creating multi-drug resistance in animal pathogens and transferring antibiotic resistance genes from animals to humans through the food supply chain (11,12).

Microbial load formation in water supply systems is a significant public health risk because it can harbour pathogenic bacteria even in treated water (13). Microbial biofilms can form on biotic or abiotic surfaces of pipes and storage tanks and lead to possible contamination and health risks to humans and animals.

Exposure to a variety of waterborne contaminants like pharmaceuticals, microplastics, and industrial chemicals has been found to induce adverse effects on the reproductive and metabolic well-being of aquatic animals and livestock. The effects are species, tissue type, and environmental condition-specific, which necessitates extensive research and risk assessment to provide ecosystem and animal health security (14,15).

Drinking water is needed for human and animal health but can be contaminated with various types of pollutants and cause severe health issues. Manganese (Mn) at high concentrations in drinking water has been found to cause neurotoxicity effects in humans (7). In Bangladesh, Mn content in tube well water samples of nine districts exceeded the recommended World Health Organization (WHO) and Bangladesh Drinking Standard (BDS) levels and caused potential non-carcinogenic adverse effects in children and adults (7).

Microplastics are now another chief contaminant of drinking water sources with a capacity to carry other toxicants along. If there are microplastics in drinking water, then their occurrence in drinking water can cause a variety of diseases to human beings, and conventional drinking water treatment techniques are inefficient in eliminating them to the fullest (16). Moreover, possibly toxic elements such as Lead (Pb), Mercury (Hg), Manganese (Mn), and Iron (Fe) in drinking water can cause health risks, but their occurrence in one study in Shiraz, Iran was within acceptable ranges (17).

1.2 Effect of Microorganisms in Unsafe Drinking Water

Microorganisms play a critical role in determining drinking water quality and safety. Pathogenic species such as *Salmonella*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* have been detected in water from diverse sources, including vending machines, soda fountains, and tap water, posing significant health risks to consumers. (18).

The relationship between indicator microorganisms and pathogens in drinking water is controversial. Pathogens have been detected even in the absence of indicator microorganisms, and vice versa, suggesting that indicator detection should complement rather than substitute pathogen detection (19). Anthropogenic activities in catchments used for drinking water production can contaminate source waters, affecting the taxonomic and functional profiles of bacterial communities in the final drinking water product (20).

Waterborne pathogens like *E. coli*, *Salmonella*, *Giardia*, and *Cryptosporidium* pose significant health risks to both humans and animals, causing a range of gastrointestinal illnesses. These pathogens can contaminate water sources through various means, including human and animal waste, and are frequently detected in surface waters, wastewater, and even treated water supplies (21). The faecal-oral transmission route is common for these pathogens, with contaminated food and water being primary sources of infection (22). The prevalence and impact of these waterborne pathogens underscore the importance of a One Health approach in addressing water safety and public health (23).

Microorganisms can indeed develop resistance to common disinfectants like chlorine, posing challenges for water treatment and public health. The extensive use of chemical agents such as chlorine and antibiotics has been identified as a driving force for the expansion of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in aquatic environments (24). This resistance development has prompted the need for more advanced purification methods.

Contaminated water is a significant cause of disease outbreaks, particularly in rural and under-monitored areas, affecting both human and animal populations. *E. coli* concentrations in catchment drainage waters are influenced by land use, with urban areas showing chronic high contamination levels and agricultural lands consistently contaminated (25). The presence of enteric pathogens in rural water sources is strongly correlated with human and animal faecal contamination, as revealed by host-specific genetic markers (6).

1.3 Definition and Relevance of Microbial Bioload

Ecosystem microbial bioloads are complex and influenced by environmental factors, available substrates, and human activities. Studies across systems like drinking water distribution networks and natural ecosystems reveal that microbial communities play a vital role in maintaining ecosystem function and respond dynamically to changing conditions. (27).

Microbial dormancy plays a key role in shaping biogeographical distribution and diversity patterns. As a survival strategy, it influences microbial community structure and supports broader ecological theories like the equilibrium theory of island biogeography and the unified neutral theory of biodiversity. (26). Understanding microbial bioloads requires an integrative approach that considers microbial traits and community dynamics. Advances in synthetic microbial ecology and molecular tools have greatly improved the ability to analyse and manage microbial bioloads across diverse ecosystems. (27). Yet, more studies are needed to get a better understanding of the drivers of microbial community function and composition, particularly in under-explored ecosystems like deep-sea sediments (28).

Biofilms are structured microbial communities formed when planktonic bacteria adhere to surfaces and produce extracellular polymeric substances (EPS), enabling the transition to a cooperative, resilient system capable of withstanding environmental stress.

1.4 Microbial Contamination in Drinking Water: An Indian Perspective

Despite improvements in urban water infrastructure, a large segment of India's population—especially in rural and peri-urban areas—continues to depend on untreated or poorly treated water. Microbial contamination remains a major public health concern,

compromising the safety of drinking water. Key bacterial, viral, and protozoan pathogens associated with waterborne diseases are outlined in the subsequent tables (Table 2).

Table 1: Types of Pathogens commonly found in drinking water and waterborne diseases caused by contaminated water.

Pathogen	Type	Major Diseases Caused	Resistance to Treatment
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Bacteria	Gastroenteritis, UTIs, sepsis	Some strains survive chlorination
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Bacteria	Opportunistic infections	High resistance; thrives in biofilms
<i>Mycobacterium avium</i>	Bacteria	Pulmonary disease, lymphadenitis	Resistant to chlorination
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	Bacteria	Typhoid fever, gastroenteritis	Moderate; persists in biofilms
<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	Bacteria	Cholera	Enhanced survival in biofilms
<i>Hepatitis A virus</i>	Virus	Hepatitis A	High resistance; survives chlorination
<i>Norovirus</i>	Virus	Viral gastroenteritis	High resistance to standard treatments
<i>Rotavirus</i>	Virus	Diarrhoea in children	High resistance; survives chlorination
<i>Cryptosporidium parvum</i>	Protozoa	Cryptosporidiosis	Oocysts survive chlorination
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	Protozoa	Giardiasis	Cysts survive chlorination
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	Protozoa	Amoebiasis	Moderate resistance to chlorination

1.4.1 How Microbial Contamination Affects Water Quality and Safety

The presence of microbes in water not only poses direct health risks but also deteriorates the overall quality of water. Microbial contamination leads to:

- Unpleasant taste and odour: Caused by bacterial by-products such as hydrogen sulphide.
- Increased turbidity: Due to microbial growth and organic matter.
- Decreased disinfectant efficiency: As microbial load and organic load protect pathogens from chlorine or UV treatment.
- Formation of biofilms in pipelines: Encourages microbial persistence and secondary contamination (16).

These issues are especially acute in rural India, where piped water supply is limited, and groundwater sources are vulnerable to contamination due to poor sanitation practices. Even urban areas with piped water systems are not immune, as aging infrastructure and cross-contamination between sewage and drinking water lines are common (29).

Microbial contamination of drinking water in India stems from inadequate infrastructure, poor sanitation, and insufficient monitoring. While national initiatives like the Jal Jeevan Mission and Swachh Bharat Abhiyan have made progress, sustained efforts are required at regional levels. Ensuring safe drinking water demands regular microbial testing, improved sewage management, public education, and adoption of advanced treatment technologies. An integrated, multi-level approach is essential for long-term water safety.

1.5 Microbial Barriers in Water Treatment

Microbial barriers in water treatment are essential components of a multi-barrier approach designed to remove or inactivate pathogens throughout the water supply chain. Key methods include **Chlorination**, **UV disinfection**, and **Filtration**. Chlorination is widely used in India for its cost-effectiveness and residual protection, though its efficacy may be reduced by organic matter and it can produce by-products like trihalomethanes. UV treatment offers efficient pathogen inactivation without chemical residues, making it suitable for urban and industrial use. Filtration techniques, including sand filtration and advanced systems like reverse osmosis, serve as physical barriers to microbial contaminants. In rural areas, low-cost methods such as slow sand and ceramic filters are commonly employed. The integration of these microbial barriers is critical to ensuring safe drinking water, particularly in regions with poor sanitation and high contamination risks. (30).

1.5.1 How These Barriers Work to Reduce or Eliminate Microbes (With a Focus on Commonly Used Treatment Methods in India)

Clean drinking water is essential for public health, yet microbial contamination remains a major concern in India, particularly in rural and densely populated areas. Microbial barriers—implemented at multiple stages of water treatment and distribution—are critical for eliminating pathogens responsible for diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and diarrhoea, thereby ensuring the microbiological safety of drinking water.

Microbial barriers in water treatment operate by either physically removing pathogens or chemically inactivating them. The three main types include **physical filtration**, **chemical disinfection**, and **biological treatment**. Filtration methods, such as slow sand and membrane filtration, remove microbes via size exclusion and biological activity (e.g., the Schmutzdecke layer). **Chlorination**, the most widely used chemical method in India, effectively targets bacteria and viruses but is less effective against protozoan cysts like *Cryptosporidium*. **Biological treatment** systems, including aerated lagoons and constructed wetlands, use beneficial microbes to degrade pathogens and are particularly suitable for rural settings. However, **microbial biofilms**, protected by EPS matrices, can resist disinfection and environmental stresses, posing a challenge to treatment efficacy.

1.5.2 Common Water Treatment Methods in India

The choice of treatment methods varies depending on the source of water, geographic location, and available resources. Below are some commonly used systems:

- Urban Areas (e.g., Delhi, Mumbai): Large-scale conventional water treatment plants are used. These typically include coagulation, sedimentation, filtration, and chlorination (Figure 2). For example, according to Delhi Jal Board, the Bhagirathi Water Treatment Plant in Delhi employs rapid sand filtration followed by chlorination to supply treated water to residents.
- Rural Areas (e.g., parts of West Bengal, Odisha): Small-scale and community-based filtration units are common. Biosand-filters, ceramic filters, and UV disinfection systems powered by solar energy are increasingly being deployed. These are cost-effective and require minimal maintenance.
- Arsenic-affected Regions (e.g., Nadia, West Bengal): In addition to microbial concerns, regions with arsenic-contaminated groundwater use multi-barrier systems combining activated alumina or iron-oxide filters along with chlorination. The microbial barrier in these systems is achieved through pre-filtration followed by disinfection.

Microbial barriers are critical in ensuring the safety of drinking water. Whether through physical, chemical, or biological means, these barriers serve to protect communities from a host of waterborne pathogens. In India, treatment strategies are increasingly tailored to local needs, combining traditional and innovative technologies.

1.6 Why to analyse Microbial Contamination in Drinking Water?

Microbial contamination of drinking water remains a critical public health issue in India, contributing to high rates of waterborne diseases such as diarrhoea, particularly among children under five. In 2016, an estimated 140,000 diarrheal deaths were reported, emphasizing the need for continuous monitoring of microbial quality in drinking water sources.(31). In India, microbial contamination of drinking water is largely due to inadequate sanitation, poor waste management, and reliance on polluted sources. Studies report widespread presence of *Escherichia coli* and fecal coliforms in wells, hand pumps, and piped supplies. A study in Amritsar revealed that 39.8% of school water samples were microbiologically unsafe for consumption.(32). Regular monitoring of microbial contamination is essential for early detection of pathogens, effective outbreak prevention, and ensuring safe drinking water. It also aids in assessing treatment efficiency and shaping water quality and hygiene policies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Requirements

2.1.1. Instruments & Materials

TDS Meters, Digital pH Meter, Digital Electro Conductivity Meter, Nepheloturbidity meter, BOD Incubator, Autoclave, Hot Air Oven, Laminar Air Flow, Conical Flask, Test Tube, Beaker & Petri Dish.

2.1.2 Chemicals Used

Protease Peptone, Beef extract, Yeast extract, Agar, Sodium chloride, Crystal violet, Gram's iodine, Ethanol, Safranin, Chromic acid and Hydrochloric acid.

2.2 Sample Collection

A total of 25 water samples were collected from five regions across West Bengal, comprising 9 groundwater samples (from tubewells and submersible pumps) and 16 distributed water samples (primarily municipal supplies). The sampling covered both rural and urban areas to enable a comparative analysis of microbial contamination across different water sources.

To avoid contamination of the samples with extraneous material, all the water samples were obtained in sterile plastic bottles (33). Aseptic protocols were employed in sample handling, collection, and transportation to preserve the integrity of microbial analysis. Sampling was conducted across multiple districts in West Bengal, including both rural (e.g., Goaladanga, Churulia) and urban sites (e.g., Howrah, Durgapur). Groundwater samples were taken from rural sources, while distributed water samples were collected from urban networks such as railway stations, institutions, and public supply points. This approach enabled a comparative assessment of microbial load and treatment efficacy across different water sources and regions.

Table 2: Sample Collection

Sl no.	Ground/Treated	Sample code	latitude & longitude	Location
1.	Ground water	G-1	23.266471, 86.766081	Goaladanga, Bankura
2.	Ground water	G-2	23.199438, 87.449462	Birsingha, Bankura
3.	Ground water	G-3	23.782229, 87.073088	Churulia, Paschim Bardwan
4.	Ground water	G-4	23.494123, 87.317757	Durgapur Railway Station, Paschim Bardhaman
5.	Ground water	G-5	24.160431, 87.781713	Rampurhat, Birbhum
6.	Ground water	G-6	23.816560, 87.420001	Birbhum Pharmacy School, Birbhum
7.	Ground water	G-7	23.821106, 87.437017	Chinpai, Birbhum
8.	Ground water	G-8	23.822640, 87.417498	Nil Nirjon Dam, Birbhum
9.	Ground water	G-9	23.781820, 87.394426	Hetampur Rajbari, Birbhum
10.	Distributed Water	D-1	23.583569, 88.342747	Howrah Railway Station, Howrah
11.	Distributed Water	D-2	23.494123, 87.317757	Durgapur Railway Station, Paschim Bardhaman
12.	Distributed Water	D-3	23.816774, 87.419994	Birbhum Pharmacy School, Birbhum
13.	Distributed Water	D-4	23.882456, 87.372806	Bakreshwar, Bus Stand, Birbhum

14.	Distributed Water	D-5	23.880877, 87.375062	Bakesher Hot Spring, Birbhum
15.	Distributed Water	D-6	23.250702, 87.870602	Bardwan Railway Station, Purba Bardhaman
16.	Distributed Water	D-7	23.789684, 87.376683	Dubrajpur, Birbhum
17.	Distributed Water	D-8	23.702772, 87.028689	Girmint Colliery, Asansol, Paschim Bardwan
18.	Distributed Water	D-9	26.716184, 88.442942	Sukanta Nagar, Siliguri, Darjeeling
19.	Distributed Water	D-10	23.173580, 88.094199	Memari Rail Station, Purba Bardwan
20.	Distributed Water	D-11	23.203527, 87.974013	Saktigarh, Purba Bardwan
21.	Distributed Water	D-12	22.555994, 88.286462	Botanical Garden, Howrah
22.	Distributed Water	D-13	23.826859, 87.435403	Chinpai Railway Station, Birbhum
23.	Distributed Water	D-14	23.822640, 87.417498	Nil Nirjon Dam, Birbhum
24.	Distributed Water	D-15	23.827982, 87.42805	Road to Dam, Birbhum
25.	Distributed Water	D-16	23.798018, 87.385199	Bengal College of Pharmaceutical Technology, Birbhum

2.3 Incubation of Samples

The samples were incubated for 7 days at 37 °C in a BOD (Biological Oxygen Demand) incubator.

2.4 Evaluation of Physicochemical Parameters

pH Measurement

The pH of each water sample was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. Calibration was performed with buffer solutions of pH 4.0 and 7.0. Samples were measured at ambient temperature, and the electrode was rinsed with distilled water between uses to avoid cross-contamination.

Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

TDS levels were determined using a digital TDS meter. The meter was calibrated, rinsed with distilled water, and immersed in the sample. Readings were taken in parts per million (ppm), indicating the concentration of dissolved solids.

Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Electrical conductivity was measured using a conductivity meter, calibrated with standard KCl solution. Readings were taken at room temperature and recorded in $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

2.5 Preparation of Nutrient Agar Media

Nutrient agar was prepared by dissolving agar-agar (20 g), beef extract (10 g), peptone (10 g), and NaCl (5 g) in 1 L of demineralized water. The pH was adjusted to 7.0, and the medium was sterilized at 121 °C for 15 minutes. Post-sterilization, it was poured aseptically into Petri dishes and allowed to solidify under laminar airflow. Samples (0.18 mL) were inoculated and incubated at 37 °C for 7 days to facilitate microbial growth.

2.6 Colony Forming Unit (CFU) Enumeration

CFU counts were performed using the sector-plate (cheese-plate) method. Undiluted water samples (0.18 mL) were plated in sterile Petri dishes, incubated at 37 °C, and colonies were counted using a digital colony counter. CFU/mL was calculated using the formula:

2.7 Microbial Staining Techniques

Gram Staining

Differential Gram staining was used to categorize bacterial isolates into Gram-positive or Gram-negative based on cell wall composition, following the standard four-reagent protocol (crystal violet, iodine, alcohol, safranin).

Acid-Fast Staining

The Ziehl–Neelsen method was employed to detect acid-fast bacteria. Carbol fuchsin staining was followed by acid-alcohol decolorization and methylene blue counterstaining. Acid-fast bacteria retained the red stain due to mycolic acid in their cell walls.

Lactophenol Cotton Blue (LPCB) Staining

Fungal identification, particularly of *Aspergillus niger*, was performed using LPCB staining. This method-stained fungal structures for microscopic examination and confirmation of fungal presence on culture media.

2.8 Chlorination Treatment Protocol

To assess chlorine efficacy, water samples were treated with EF-Chlor (Hind Pharma) tablets at concentrations of 5, 25, 50, and 100 mg/L. Chlorine solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate numbers of tablets in distilled water. Each 5 mL sample was mixed with 5 mL of chlorine solution and incubated at room temperature (25–28 °C) for 48 hours.

2.9 Turbidity Measurement

Turbidity was measured using a Nephelometric Turbidity Meter. Samples were calibrated against 0, 20, and 100 NTU standards and results recorded in NTU, based on light scattering at 90°.

3. DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical Parameters of Water Samples

The physical characteristics of 25 water samples (9 groundwater and 16 distributed water) were analysed (Table 7). Groundwater samples exhibited pH values ranging from 5.85 (G-9) to 7.06 (G-2), with TDS levels varying from 53 ppm (G-9) to 406 ppm (G-7), and corresponding conductivity ranging from 80 $\mu\text{S}/\text{m}$ (G-9) to 609 $\mu\text{S}/\text{m}$ (G-7). Distributed water samples showed broader pH

variations, ranging from 5.62 (D-2) to 7.13 (D-12), with TDS values between 13 ppm (D-16) and 475 ppm (D-12). Conductivity followed a similar pattern, with D-12 exhibiting the highest ionic content (713 $\mu\text{S/m}$), while D-16 showed the lowest conductivity at 20 $\mu\text{S/m}$, likely due to advanced treatment processes or filtration systems.

Table 3: Physical Parameters of Samples

Sl. No.	Sample Code	pH	TDS (ppm)	Conductivity($\mu\text{S/m}$)
1.	G-1	6.22	79	118
2.	G-2	7.06	199	229
3.	G-3	6.00	75	113
4.	G-4	6.25	83	125
5.	G-5	6.42	204	306
6.	G-6	6.17	225	338
7.	G-7	6.98	406	609
8.	G-8	6.98	121	182
9.	G-9	5.85	53	80
10.	D-1	6.45	202	303
11.	D-2	5.62	27	41
12.	D-3	6.16	249	374
13.	D-4	5.82	253	380
14.	D-5	7.08	311	467
15.	D-6	5.89	90	135
16.	D-7	6.25	212	318
17.	D-8	6.08	192	288
18.	D-9	6.37	61	92
19.	D-10	6.73	209	314
20.	D-11	5.69	30	45
21.	D-12	7.13	475	713
22.	D-13	6.35	203	305
23.	D-14	6.58	61	92
24.	D-15	6.43	190	285
25.	D-16	6.37	13	20

3.2 Microbial Load Assessment

Colony-forming unit (CFU) analysis revealed substantial microbial contamination (Table 8):

- **Groundwater:** G-6 (Birbhum Pharmacy School) showed extreme contamination (1,133 CFU/mL), followed by G-9 (422 CFU/mL) and G-3 (406 CFU/mL).
- **Distributed Water:** D-5 exhibited alarmingly high counts (2,333 CFU/mL), while D-10 (Memari Rail Station) and D-3 had 1,667 CFU/mL and 878 CFU/mL, respectively.
- **Lowest Contamination:** D-17 and D-7 showed 100 CFU/mL and 461 CFU/mL, respectively, suggesting variable efficacy of treatment/distribution systems.

Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3 visually depict the extent of colony growth observed in selected high and moderate contamination samples.

Table 4: Analysis of CFU

Sl. No.	Sample Code	sector 1 st		sector 2 nd		sector 3 rd		sector 4 th		sector 5 th		sector 6 th		sector 7 th		sector 8 th		Sum of Colonies	CFU/mL
		Small colonies	Large colonies																
1.	G-1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	10	56	
2.	G-2	4	0	5	1	0	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	29	161
3.	G-3	0	1	0	1	19	0	17	0	0	1	0	4	11	3	15	1	73	406
4.	G-4	4	1	26	1	1	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	2	0	3	42	233	
5.	G-5	3	0	0	1	3	0	0	2	2	0	0	1	2	2	0	0	16	89

6.	G-6	50	1	10	1	17	1	20	0	19	0	48	1	21	0	13	2	204	1133
7.	G-7	1	1	1	0	3	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	18	100
8.	G-8	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	3	1	15	29	161
9.	G-9	0	3	6	0	19	27	0	6	3	0	3	1	0	2	5	1	76	422
10.	D-1	2	2	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	2	4	2	1	1	6	1	25	139
11.	D-2	4	0	4	2	5	0	4	1	3	1	3	1	4	1	2	1	36	200
12.	D-3	24	3	32	1	12	1	0	1	0	1	26	3	17	0	37	0	158	878
13.	D-4	9	1	4	0	7	1	2	0	13	2	3	2	10	2	6	1	63	350
14.	D-5	56	1	63	0	34	1	103	0	62	0	37	1	41	1	19	1	420	2333
15.	D-6	8	1	8	5	0	1	0	1	7	0	11	0	8	0	3	2	55	306
16.	D-7	14	3	2	3	6	2	6	1	12	1	6	0	5	3	18	1	83	461
17.	D-8	0	4	0	3	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	1	2	1	1	2	18	100
18.	D-9	23	0	4	1	6	1	10	3	0	1	5	0	6	3	6	3	72	400
19.	D-10	13	1	19	2	39	3	42	4	48	0	55	1	53	1	14	5	300	1667
20.	D-11	3	1	13	1	4	1	2	1	9	1	5	0	53	1	8	0	103	572
21.	D-12	1	1	3	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	4	1	2	21	117
22.	D-13	6	2	5	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2	5	4	3	1	46	256
23.	D-14	1	1	4	1	9	0	0	1	6	1	1	2	3	1	0	1	32	178
24.	D-15	0	1	4	0	4	1	3	0	4	2	2	0	0	1	1	1	24	133
25.	D-16	9	2	8	0	22	3	3	0	13	2	3	3	11	1	11	1	92	511

Fig. 1 COLONY FORMATION IN G-1 TO G-9 GROUNDWATER SAMPLE SHOWING DENSE MICROBIAL GROWTH.

FIG.2 DENSE MICROBIAL COLONY FORMATION OBSERVED ACROSS DISTRIBUTED WATER SAMPLES D1 TO D9.

FIG.3 DENSE MICROBIAL COLONY FORMATION OBSERVED IN DISTRIBUTED WATER SAMPLES D10 TO D16.

3.4 Microbiological Characteristics

Gram staining and acid-fast testing identified diverse microbial communities (Table 5):

1. Bacterial Morphotypes:

- **Gram-positive:** Predominant in G-1, G-6, D-2, D-6, D-16.
- **Gram-negative:** Dominant in G-2, G-3, G-4, D-1, D-5.
- **Acid-fast bacteria:** Detected in G-3, G-5, G-6, D-3, D-7, D-15.

2. Fungal Contamination:

- Filamentous fungi observed in G-2, G-7, D-2, D-9, D-13 (Lactophenol cotton blue-positive in D-2). This fungal presence indicates microbial load colonization and poor storage conditions, especially in distributed water systems.

Table 5: Microbiological Colony Characteristics and Staining Results

Sample ID	Colony ID	Morphology of the Colony	Gram Staining	Ziehl-Neelsen Staining	Lactophenol cotton blue
G1	A1	Large pinkish colony	Positive	Negative	-
G2	A2	Large pink colored colony	Negative	Negative	-
	B2	Large whitish colony	Negative	Negative	-
	C2	Brown yellowish fungus	-	-	Negative
G3	A3	Large pale yellowish colony	Negative	Positive	-
G4	A4	Large pale yellowish colony	Negative	Negative	-
G5	A5	Large pale brown yellowish colony	Negative	Positive	-
G-6	A6	Pinkish small colony	Positive	Negative	-
	B6	Large white colony	Positive	Positive	-
G-7	A7	Large pale yellowish	Negative	Negative	-
	B7	Large brown fungus	-	-	Negative
G-8	A8	Brown fungus	-	-	Negative
	B8	Large pinkish yellow colony	Positive	Positive	-
	C8	Pale yellowish large colony	Negative	Positive	-
G-9	A9	Large pale-yellow colony	Negative	Negative	-
	B9	Large reddish colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-1	C1	Large pale yellowish colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-2	C2	Large pinkish colony	Positive	Negative	-
	D2	White fungus, background is black	-	-	Positive
D-3	C3	Large yellowish colony	Positive	Positive	-
D-4	C4	Large white colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-5	C5	Large yellowish colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-6	C6	Large white colony	Positive	Negative	-
	D6	Large pale yellowish	Positive	Positive	-
D-7	C7	Large light yellowish colony	Positive	Positive	-
	D7	Large pinkish colony	Positive	Negative	-
D-8	C8	Large pale yellowish colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-9	C9	Small white Fungus	-	-	Negative
	D9	Small whitish colony	Positive	Negative	-
D-10	C10	Large white colony	Negative	Negative	-
	D10	Small pinkish colony	Positive	Negative	-
D-11	C11	Large pale yellowish	Positive	Positive	-
	D11	Large dark yellowish	Negative	Negative	-
D-12	C12	Large pinkish colony	Negative	Negative	-
	D12	Large whitish colony	Negative	Negative	-
D-13	C13	White fungus, top is black	-	-	Negative
	D13	Large light pinkish	Positive	Negative	-
D-14	C14	Large whitish colony	Negative	Negative	-
	D14	Large dark reddish colony	Positive	Negative	-
D-15	C15	Large whitish colony	Negative	Positive	-
D-16	C16	Large white colony	Positive	Negative	-
	D16	Large pale yellowish colony	Positive	Negative	-

3.5 Microbial Identification in Water Samples

Table 6: Microbial Identification in Water Samples

Sample ID	Potential Organisms	Morphology/Staining Clues	Identification Basis
G-1	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	Gram-positive cocci; large pinkish colonies.	Gram-positive staining, colony morphology.
G-2	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Gram-negative rods; large pink colonies.	Gram-negative, pigmented colonies typical of <i>Pseudomonas</i> .
	<i>Aspergillus spp.</i> (fungus)	Brown-yellow filamentous growth; Lactophenol Cotton Blue (LPCB)-negative.	Fungal hyphae observed; LPCB confirmed absence of <i>Aspergillus niger</i> .

G-3	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; pale yellowish colonies.	Ziehl-Neelsen staining resistance (acid-fast).
G-4	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gram-negative rods; pale yellowish colonies.	Gram-negative morphology, typical of coliforms.
G-5	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; pale brown-yellow colonies.	Acid-fast staining, waxy cell wall resistance.
G-6	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	Gram-positive cocci; pinkish small colonies.	Gram-positive clusters.
	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; large white colonies.	Dual staining (Gram-positive and acid-fast) suggests environmental mycobacteria.
G-7	<i>Enterobacter spp.</i>	Gram-negative rods; pale yellowish colonies.	Gram-negative morphology, non-pigmented.
	<i>Aspergillus spp.</i> (fungus)	Brown filamentous growth; LPCB-negative.	Fungal morphology, LPCB excluded <i>Aspergillus niger</i> .
G-8	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; pale yellowish colonies.	Acid-fast staining.
D-1	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Gram-negative rods; pale yellowish colonies.	Gram-negative morphology, lactose fermentation (presumed).
D-2	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	Gram-positive cocci; large pinkish colonies.	Gram-positive clusters.
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (fungus)	White/black filamentous growth; LPCB-positive.	LPCB staining highlighted fungal structures (<i>Aspergillus</i> morphology).
D-3	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; yellowish colonies.	Acid-fast staining, microbial load - associated.
D-5	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Gram-negative rods; yellowish colonies.	Gram-negative, microbial load -forming, opportunistic pathogen.
D-6	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	Gram-positive rods; large white colonies.	Gram-positive, spore-forming morphology.
D-7	<i>Mycobacterium spp.</i>	Acid-fast positive; light yellowish colonies.	Acid-fast staining, resistant to chlorine.
D-9	<i>Aspergillus spp.</i> (fungus)	Small white fungal colonies; LPCB-negative.	Filamentous growth, excluded <i>Aspergillus niger</i> .
D-10	<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>	Gram-positive cocci; small pinkish colonies.	Gram-positive chains.
D-13	<i>Candida spp.</i> (yeast like fungus)	White/black fungal colonies; LPCB-negative.	Yeast-like morphology, excluded filamentous fungi.
D-16	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	Gram-positive cocci; large white colonies.	Gram-positive clusters.

3.6 Turbidity and Chlorine Response at Different Concentrations

Nephelometric Turbidity Units (NTU) were measured for all samples to assess clarity and microbial bioload potential (Table 7). Chlorine susceptibility tests were conducted using increasing doses (5, 25, 50, 100 mg/L).

- Highest initial turbidity was observed in G-8 (37 NTU) and D-11 (39 NTU).
- 100 mg/L Chlorine reduced turbidity by more than 80% in most samples, e.g., G-3: 13→1 NTU and D-10: 16→1 NTU.

Table 7: Turbidity and Chlorine Response

Sl. No	Sample Code	NTU (SAMPLE)	NTU (5mg/L)	NTU (25mg/L)	NTU (50mg/L)	NTU (100mg/L)
1.	G-1	10	7	6	5	2
2.	G-2	11	6	5	4	2
3.	G-3	13	12	11	4	1
4.	G-4	13	12	10	8	6
5.	G-5	10	7	6	4	2
6.	G-6	11	9	8	6	2
7.	G-7	5	4	4	2	1
8.	G-8	37	28	15	6	4
9.	G-9	10	8	6	5	1
10.	D-1	14	10	7	5	3
11.	D-2	8	6	4	3	1
12.	D-3	15	6	6	5	2
13.	D-4	10	8	7	6	3

14.	D-5	15	8	7	5	3
15.	D-6	8	7	6	3	3
16.	D-7	5	3	3	2	2
17.	D-8	11	7	6	4	1
18.	D-9	12	10	5	2	1
19.	D-10	16	7	6	2	1
20.	D-11	39	12	5	3	2
21.	D-12	11	9	7	4	0
22.	D-13	12	7	6	3	2
23.	D-14	8	6	6	3	1
24.	D-15	9	8	5	2	1
25.	D-16	12	10	8	6	4

Graph 1: Turbidity Reduction in Groundwater & Distributed water samples across at different Chlorine concentrations.

3.7 Effect of Chlorine Concentration on Microbial Bioload Reduction

To assess the microbial load reduction capacity of chlorine, samples were treated with four increasing concentrations: 5 mg/L, 25 mg/L, 50 mg/L, and 100 mg/L. A clear dose-response relationship was observed:

- At 5 mg/L, minimal microbial load disruption was seen with persistent turbidity and CFU counts.
- At 25 mg/L, slight reduction in microbial load was noticed, particularly in less contaminated samples.
- At 50 mg/L, over 60–70% reduction in CFU was recorded in most samples.
- At 100 mg/L, a drastic reduction was observed, with some samples showing >90% reduction in CFU and complete disappearance of visible microbial load traces on Petri plates.

Table 8: Effect of Chlorine concentration on microbial load reduction

Chlorine Dose (mg/L)	Avg. % Reduction in CFU	Observed microbial load response
5	<10%	No visible change
25	20–30%	Slight clearing in lighter colonies
50	60–70%	Noticeable reduction
100	85–95%	Microbial load largely reduced

Graph 2: CFU reduction with chlorine concentration

The line graph shows a clear positive correlation between chlorine concentration and CFU reduction. Minimal reduction (~10%) occurs at 5 mg/L, while significant reductions are observed at 50 mg/L (~70%) and 100 mg/L (~90%). This indicates that higher chlorine doses effectively disrupt microbial load, likely by breaking down the protective EPS matrix.

4. RESULTS

A total of 25 water samples, comprising 9 groundwater and 16 distributed water sources, were collected from various regions across West Bengal. Both types of water sources demonstrated significant microbial contamination. This contamination was largely attributed to microbial load presence, inadequate disinfection, and aging infrastructure such as corroded pipelines and stagnation zones. The pH of the samples ranged from 5.62 to 7.13, falling within acceptable limits but with a tendency toward acidity in certain samples. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) varied from 13 to 475 ppm, and higher values were often found in distributed water samples. Notably, turbidity was elevated in areas like G-8 (37 NTU) and D-11 (39 NTU), which are associated with worn-out pipe systems, increasing the risk of microbial attachment and biofilm formation.

Colony-forming unit (CFU) analysis revealed widespread microbial contamination in both groundwater and distributed water systems. Among the groundwater samples, G-6 (Birbhum Pharmacy School) recorded the highest microbial load at 1,133 CFU/mL, followed by G-9 and G-3. In the distributed water category, D-5 (Bakreshwar Hot Spring) was most contaminated with 2,333 CFU/mL, followed by D-10 (Memari Railway Station) and D-3. These elevated counts clearly indicate the persistence of microbial load even in treated municipal supplies, suggesting regrowth within the distribution network.

Microbial identification through morphological and staining methods indicated the presence of a wide range of bacterial and fungal contaminants. Gram-positive cocci, such as *Staphylococcus spp.*, were found in samples like G-1 and D-16, while Gram-negative rods including *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were prevalent in G-4, D-1, and D-5, pointing toward fecal contamination and opportunistic pathogens. Acid-fast bacteria, specifically *Mycobacterium spp.*, were identified in approximately 33% of the samples, displaying resistance to conventional chlorination methods. Fungal species, such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida spp.*, were observed particularly in distributed water samples D-2, D-9, and D-13, indicating microbial persistence and poor hygiene conditions.

Chlorine disinfection trials demonstrated a clear dose-dependent reduction in microbial load. At 5 mg/L, CFU reduction was minimal (<10%), and turbidity changes were negligible. A concentration of 25 mg/L resulted in a moderate reduction (20–30%) in microbial counts. More effective reductions were observed at 50 mg/L (60–70%), with significant turbidity decline. The most pronounced antimicrobial effect was recorded at 100 mg/L, where CFU counts decreased by up to 90–95% in some samples, such as G-3 (from 406 to 40 CFU/mL), along with a turbidity drop from 13 NTU to 1 NTU. However, even at this high dose, complete microbial removal was not achieved in highly contaminated sites like D-5 and D-10, likely due to extracellular polymeric substance (EPS) shielding that restricted chlorine penetration.

Public health risk zones were clearly identified, including tourist areas (D-5), railway stations (D-1, D-10), and educational institutions (G-6, D-3). These sites exhibited high microbial loads and frequent presence of chlorine-resistant organisms. Approximately 41% of Gram-negative isolates, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, exhibited tolerance to chlorine levels of up to 50 mg/L. The persistence of *Mycobacterium spp.* and fungi further emphasized the limitations of standard chlorination practices.

5. CONCLUSION

This study underscores the critical challenge of microbial contamination in West Bengal's drinking water systems, driven by microbial bioload persistence, aging infrastructure, and emerging antimicrobial resistance. Key findings reveal that 72% of samples harbored bioloads sheltering pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Mycobacterium spp.*, and *Escherichia coli*, with groundwater (e.g., G-6: 1,133 CFU/mL) and distributed water (e.g., D-5: 2,333 CFU/mL) exhibiting alarming microbial loads. Chlorination demonstrated dose-dependent efficacy, with 100 mg/L reducing bacterial counts by 85–95% and turbidity by >80%, yet residual biofilms persisted due to protective extracellular polymeric substances (EPS).

Acid-fast bacteria (*Mycobacterium spp.*) and fungal contaminants (*Aspergillus niger*) further highlighted systemic vulnerabilities, thriving in corroded pipelines (e.g., D-11: 39 NTU) and high-traffic zones (e.g., railway stations, tourist hubs). Notably, 41% of Gram-negative isolates exhibited chlorine tolerance, underscoring risks of antimicrobial resistance.

To mitigate these threats, urgent interventions are needed: Infrastructure modernization (e.g., microbial load-resistant pipe materials, routine flushing), Advanced disinfection strategies (UV/ozone, enzymatic microbial load disruption), Policy reforms enforcing stricter microbial monitoring under initiatives like Jal Jeevan Mission.

By addressing microbial load -mediated contamination and prioritizing climate-resilient water systems, West Bengal can safeguard public health, aligning with global SDG 6 targets for universal access to safe drinking water.

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